

The Influence of Training, Job Security, Career Development Opportunities and Performance Appraisal on Turnover Intention among Hospital Employees in Kuala Lumpur

Jasmani Binti Mohd Yunus

Universiti Utara Malaysia, College of Business,
Sintok, Kedah, Malaysia

Abdul Jumaat Bin Mahajar

School of Management and Business,
Manipal International University, Nilai,
Negri Sembilan, Malaysia

ABSTRACT

Employee turnover has gained considerable attention from various industries in Malaysia. The main objective of this study is to explore potential influence of training, job security, career development opportunities and performance appraisal towards turnover intention among hospital employees in Kuala Lumpur. By identifying significant influences of training, job security, career development opportunities and performance appraisal on hospital employees turnover intention, it will help to create awareness to hospital on the importance of those practices in building human capital. There are 274 hospital employees from five respective hospitals in Kuala Lumpur were selected as samples. The data were collected using five-point Likert Scale's self-administered questionnaires. There are two types of data techniques adapted for this research which is descriptive and inferential analysis techniques. Descriptive analysis technique is used to identify the background of respondents in the aspect of age, gender, marital status, years of experience, and qualification. However inferential analysis is used to determine the significant relationship between training, job security, career development opportunities, performance appraisal and turnover intention among hospital employees in Kuala Lumpur. The result of this study shows that there is a strong correlation between training and turnover intention. The results also revealed that there is a weak correlation between performance appraisal, career development opportunities, job security and turnover intention. This study helps to identify factors contributing towards

hospital employees turnover intention in Kuala Lumpur and recognise few recommendation to reduce turnover intention.

Keywords: *Training; Job Security; Performance; Development*

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Healthcare services in Malaysia consist of government-run public health clinics and hospitals and private medical services are mainly provided by private health clinics or general practices and hospitals. Public sector health services are administered by the Ministry of Health through its central, state and district health offices. Meanwhile, Public health clinics are under the coordination and administration of their respective district health offices. General practices are usually solo practices run by non-specialist doctors and similarly to private hospitals, they are mainly sited in urban areas. Both healthcare sectors are still expanding. The Malaysian healthcare sector is set to be transformed from a social service and consumer of wealth to a private sector-driven engine for economic growth. Demand of healthcare is likely to expand as the elderly increase in number, consumer awareness of healthcare service grows and access to services improves.

Table 1.0 Hospitals & Number of Beds in Malaysia

Year	Number Of Public		Number Of Private	
	Hospitals	Beds	Hospitals	Beds
2013	134	35,739	223	11,367
2014	136	37,793	209	11,689
2015	137	38,004	217	13,186

(Source: Health Facts 2015, Ministry of Health Malaysia)

Most of the hospitals in Malaysia offers a comprehensive range of services for paediatric & maternal services, heart disease followed by mental illness, cerebrovascular disease/stroke, road traffic injuries and cancers. Under the 10th Malaysian Plan, the Ministry of Health has prioritised the development of cardiac, emergency and oncology services for the nation. The ratio of medical doctors in hospitals (excluding housemen) to population is 1: 1870. Seventy four per cent of these doctors are serving in the public hospitals with 26% in the private hospitals (Clinical research Centre, Ministry of Health (2014)). The Ministry of health has invested heavily in developing the capacity and capability of human workforce. This is especially for specialist services whereby there were 2,836 specialists working in the Ministry of Health (MOH) hospitals, 7030 specialists in the universities setting and 2,692 specialists in the private sector (Ministry of Health, 2014). The Malaysian government wants to foster growth in public and private healthcare services especially to a more profitable medical technology such as medical devices, diagnostic equipment and healthcare information technology.

Turnover intention issue has not been solved which means that until now it still remains as one of the top issue that has been studied and explored more compare to any other Human Resource Management (HRM) phenomenon. However, reason for turnover intention being so important and its influences to employees lead researchers from time to time return to restudying deeper into this matter. Moreover, nearly all of the available researchers on employee turnover is not attempts to address the question of why some workplace experience higher turnover rates than others but rather on understanding the process of which individuals choose to quit or stay (Shaw, Gupta & Delery, 2005). Mathieu and Meneze (2005), mentioned that common issues in turnover which later leads to difficulty in access to organizational-level measures of aggregate-level constructs are the reasons why limited

studies on organizational variables such as human resource management practices.

According to researchers Qurehi & Rasli (2014), Human Resource Management Practices (HRM practices) can affect employee's turnover intention. Additionally, as stated by researchers Quresh et al. (2013), employers who practice the proper HRM practices in an organization and employees who is appreciated by employer with training practices, job security, career development opportunities, and performance appraisal will definitely respond positively by remaining on their present job.

Although employees often change jobs due to career advancement and better training programs, the management cannot be dependent on those practices to retain employees for a long term production. Having similar opinion Quresh at al. (2013) & Moncarz et. al., (2009), pointed out that decrease in turnover rate of the employees is possible if and only if standard performance appraisal and proper training are delivered by employer to employee, besides, employee retention can be preserved by giving better compensation practices and giving promotions. Similar to that Min et.al., (2007), found that job security and increasing level of experience will weaken employee's turnover rate. Those employees who have a thought that they do not be in the right place in an organization will shortly leave. For this reason, investigating the relationship between training, job security, career development opportunities, performance appraisal and employee's turnover intentions will be essential for the management since it could lead to actual employee losses.

According to the National Health Facts, there are only about 25 thousand medical officers in Malaysia giving rise to the ratio of one doctor to 1,100 patients, and they cater for 80% of Malaysian (Ministry of Health, 2008). Unfortunately, approximately 300 hospital employees leave the public service annually to work in the private sector and some leave the medical profession altogether . In the year 2011, a total of 441 Medical Officers and Medical Specialists have resigned from Ministry, which are 311 and 130 respectively. This number contributes to 2.08% of the total Medical Officer and Medical Specialists in Ministry of Health. Turnover of hospital employees is costly for both the employer and the employees. This is because the employer (government/private) would find the replacement and hidden costs will increase meanwhile the employees would find increment in the monetary and

psychological costs taxing (Mitchell et.al., 2001). . Eleven HRM practices adopted by Kuo (2004), found that employment security, training and performance appraisal are regarded as three of the main practices for impacting hospital performance. Wheeler, Harris and Harvey (2010) cited that organizations should enhance their business performances through practicing strategic HRM practices as it have the ability in reducing employee's turnover which was also highlighted by Chang & Chen, (2002); Moynihan, Wright & Gardner (2003) in discussions on HRM in recent years. Therefore, this research paper aims to gain better understanding and provide further insights into the role of employee's identification with their organization and how evaluation on training, job security, career development opportunities and performance appraisal affects turnover intention of hospital employees in Kuala Lumpur.

1.1 Research Objectives

- i) To examine the relationship between training and turnover intention among hospitals employees.
- ii) To investigate the relationship of job security towards turnover intention among hospitals employees.
- iii) To examine the relationship of career development opportunities and turnover intention among hospitals employees.
- iv) To determine the relationship of performance appraisal towards turnover intention among hospitals employees.

2.0 Literature Review

According to Robbins et.al., (2005), turnover is the permanent withdrawal either voluntary or involuntary from an organization. Abassi and Hollman (2000) adding in that employee turnover can be considered as an employee cycle in a particular industry whereby there will be rotation between employment and unemployment situation and also between organizations, jobs and occupations. there is a relationship exist between training and turnover. Sherman & Bohlander (1992), found that training in managerial competencies, skills and programs with growth opportunities will be used to increase job commitment and reduce employee turnover. Berntson et al. (2010) & Helliriegal, (2001), stated that a

relationship is widely confirmed when turnover intention was measured to get to know one's response on job security and it is assumed that employees react to a high level of job security over time with a high level of turnover intention. According to Helmi, (2006), similar study carried out by 'University of Technology MARA', Malaysia on hotel employee revealed that other predictors such as career development opportunities program besides having good HR practices, is essential to oppose turnover intentions. Those organizations that fail to provide satisfaction for employees in term of career growth will indirectly leads to the prospects of employment elsewhere which more attractive than the current job. Zimmerman, (2009) shares the similar view by stating that it is proven that there is a significant relationship between employee's job performance management and turnover intention which results revealed in a survey conducted by collecting data from 165 respondents on performance management and turnover intention.

3.0 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

This research is using a quantitative research as it is the best method to measure the influence of the variables. Cohen et.al, (2000) stated that survey research is one of the methods that use scientific sampling and questionnaire design uses statistical method for measurement. Cohen also explained that the benefit for quantitative research is it provides estimation of population at large. A quantitative research will be able to gather valuable data and prove the correlation between training, job security, career development opportunities, and performance appraisal and employee turnover statistically. Therefore, a set of questionnaires was design and to ensure the questionnaire reliability, a pilot test was run before distributing to actual respondents.

3.2 Research Instrument

Instrument used in this research is a questionnaire to gather the data from the research sample. The questionnaire consists of 31 questions which are divided into three sections. A total of 274 questionnaires were distributed via hardcopy. Data collection method was taken into consideration while structuring the questionnaire so that the questionnaire distributed could be collected easily and conveniently. Respondents participated by selecting from the multiple choice responses using a 5 point Likert Scale which

varying from 1 to 5 (1=Strongly Disagree, 2=Disagree, 3=Neutral, 4=Agree and 5=Strongly Agree). This method is chosen because it is not only quick and easy but less costly. Johns (2010) says that Likert Scale used to measure the broader attitudes and values. The gathered data was analysed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

The population for this study consists of 950 hospital staff. The sample size in this study is determined by setting the number of respondents to 274 hospital employees. Sampling involves procedures which used a small number of samples as representative of the whole population. As proposed by Krecjie and Morgan (1970), for a population of 950 staffs, 274 samples are adequate to be used in the data analysis. The respondents are individuals who work in five respective hospitals. Simple random sampling was used in this study. It randomly selected all the respondents throughout the samples. This type of sampling was chosen as equal chances to be included in the sample for each element in the population are guaranteed (Zikmund, 2009).

3.3 Reliability Test

Reliability test is done to identify the internal consistency of the items in every section of the questionnaires. The questionnaire is considered to be reliable when it is repeated application results in consistent scores and the stronger the relation between items, the higher the reliability of the scale. According to Uma Sekaran (2003), the closer the reliability coefficient to 1.00, is the better. In general, reliabilities less than 0.60 are considered poor, those in the range of over 0.70 are considered good and acceptable. The pilot test on 30 respondents was conducted among hospital employees from five respective hospitals in Kuala Lumpur. Randomly select the targeted respondent for this test and their willingness to participate in the research was confirmed.

Table 2.0 Reliability Test

No	Variables	Cronbacj Alpha
1	Training (T1 – T5)	0.86
2	Job security (J1 – J5)	0.78
3	Career Development (C1-C5)	0.88
4	Performance Appraisal (P1-P5)	0.89
5	Turnover Intention (I1_I5)	0.90

Table 2.0 above shows all the Independent Variables (Training, Job security, Career development and Performance appraisal) and the dependent variable (Turnover intention) showed the cronbach alpha are more than 0.70 which shows that all the questions pertaining those variables are reliable.

3.4 Validity Test

Content validity ensures that the measures include an adequate and representative set of items that tap the concept. In this study, instruments for all the related items have adopted from previous literature. For example, instrument for Training was adopted from *Aksu & Yildiz (2011)*, *G.R. Oldham (1986)* for Job Security, *Briscoe (2006)* for Career Development Opportunities variable, *Evan (1978)* for Performance Appraisal and Turnover Intention scale is adopted. To ensure the questions are relevant to be given to the respondents, the questionnaires had been analysed and approved by four experts in their own field. The questionnaire was given to the Hospital Directors, Head of Departments and three Directors from Ministry of Health. After three consecutive meetings with all the experts and after alterations and modification of the questions in the questionnaire, the final questions being used for the study.

4.0 Findings

Table 3.0 Demographic Profile of Respondents

Demographic Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender		
• Male	99	36.1
• Female	175	63.9
Age		
• More than 16 less than 20	24	8.8
• Between 21-30	115	42.0
• Between 31-40	95	34.7
• More than 41	40	14.6
Marital Status		
• Married	151	55.1
• Unmarried	102	37.2
• Widow	21	7.7
Educational Qualifications		
• SPM	32	11.7
• STPM	38	13.9
• DIPLOMA	103	37.6
• DEGREE	69	25.2
• MASTER	26	9.5
• PHD	6	2.2
Salary Scale		
• RM1500-RM2000	89	32.5
• RM2500-RM3000	114	41.6
• RM3500-RM4000	55	20.1
• Above 4500	16	5.8
Tenure (Years of Service)		
• Less than 1 year	32	11.7
• 1-3 years	97	35.4
• More than 3 years	88	32.1
• Others (please specify)	57	20.8

There are two hundred and seventy four hospital employees that participated in this study. As shown in Table 3.0, the total output obtained from the frequency and percentage analysis done by using the SPSS software version 20.0. The respondents background was divided into six categories respectively gender, age, civil status, educational qualification, salary scale and years of working experience. The descriptive analysis shows that female respondent stands as the highest among all. This can be seen in the above table as female reach 63.9% whereas male respondent stands for 36.1% only. This indicates that more than half of the hospital employees that participate in this study are female compare to male.

The highest range of age among hospital staff participants are ranged between (21-30) age group as they reach for 42%. This is not a surprise as understandably, young people or the youth group tend to voice out their rights. Whereas employees in age between (31-40) is not much lesser than the youth by 34.7% followed by employees in age group more than 41 is 14.6%. The least employees who participated are the ones ranged between (16-20) which only reach for 8.8% among the total employees. This is mainly due to the fact of lacking of qualification, thus less awareness of job rights.

Focusing on the participants marital status, 55.1% of the respondents are married, whereas 37.2% seems to be single and 7.7% left considered to be widows. This indicates, married participants are the most participated for this study. In terms of educational background of the participants, majority are qualified with Diploma that is 37.6% followed by 25.2% with Bachelor Degree. SPM holders are 11.7% lesser than Bachelor Degree and not much difference as seen for the STPM holders as they 13.9% higher than SPM holders who participated. Whereas Masters Holder participants are even lesser with 9.5%, same goes to PhD holders with only 2.2% of participants. Focusing on the participants monthly salary range reflect that participants with salary range in between RM2500-RM3000 is the

highest of 41.6% meanwhile salary range of RM1500-RM2000 stands for 32.5% which slight difference compare to the highest salary range. Participants with salary range of RM3500-RM4000 shows 20.1%. However the lowest participant who participated involves those with the highest salary range of above RM4500 which stands with 5.8% only.

Based on the analysis made, 35.4% participants experience between 1-3 years of working in hospitals whereas 32.1% experienced more than 3 years' experience meanwhile only 11.7% participants work for less than 1 year.

4.0 Correlation Analysis between Dependent & Independent Variable

Correlations		MTR	MJS	MPA	MCDO	MTI
MTR	Pearson Correlation	1	.032	.271**	.118	.696**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.598	.000	.052	.000
	N	274	274	274	274	274
MJS	Pearson Correlation	.032	1	.076	.148*	.125*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.598		.213	.014	.038
	N	274	274	274	274	274
MPA	Pearson Correlation	.271**	.076	1	.035	.263**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.213		.562	.000
	N	274	274	274	274	274
MCDO	Pearson Correlation	.118	.148*	.035	1	.185**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.052	.014	.562		.002
	N	274	274	274	274	274
MTI	Pearson Correlation	.696**	.125*	.263**	.185**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.038	.000	.002	
	N	274	274	274	274	274
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).						
*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).						

MTR : Training
MJS : Job Security
MPA : Performance Appraisal
MCDO : Career Development Opportunities
MTI : Turnover Intention

The above table explains the relationship between Turnover Intention (dependent variable) among hospital employees and HRM practices includes training, job security, career development opportunities and performance appraisal (independent variable) in hospitals. As indicated in the above table, the relationship between dependent and independent

variable shows positive relationship. Based on the Correlation Analysis, the degree of significant of each independent variable in relation to employee's turnover intention is 0.696 for training, job security as 0.125 followed by performance appraisal is 0.263 and career development opportunities as 0.185. Training has a greater relationship with turnover intention among

hospital employees followed by performance appraisal, career development opportunities and job security.

5.0 Regression Analysis

Table 5.0 Summary of Regression Analysis

MODEL SUMMARY

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.713 ^a	.508	.501	.61421

ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	104.849	4	26.212	69.481	.000 ^a
	Residual	101.483	269	.377		
	Total	206.332	273			

a. Predictors: (Constant), MCDO, MPA, MJS, MTR

b. Dependent Variable: MTI

COEFFICIENTS

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.278	.248		1.118	.265
	MTR	.682	.046	.663	14.822	.000
	MJS	.082	.042	.085	1.959	.051
	MPA	.061	.037	.073	1.646	.101
	MCDO	.090	.042	.092	2.115	.035

a. Dependent Variable: MTI

Table 5.0 illustrated the result of regression analysis to determine the influence of training, job security, career development opportunities and performance appraisal on turnover intention among hospital employees. According to the above table, the adjusted R square shows result of 0.508 (50.8%). This results describes that the four independent variables includes training, job security, performance appraisal and career development opportunities are the main factors contributing towards hospital employee turnover intention. It also refer that 50.8% of the variance had been founded and explained by these independent variable. However, there are remaining 49.2% is unexplained in this study.

The overall conclusion of the regression analysis says that only 50.8% of HRM practices include training, job

security, performance appraisal and career development opportunities have been identified towards hospital employee's turnover intention. There are still 49.2% remaining of other factors that lead to turnover intention among hospital employees. The F value is 69.481 and significant at .000. The most influential factor is training with the beta value of 0.663, $p = 0.000 < 0.05$ and job security with beta value of 0.085, $p = 0.051 > 0.05$. For performance appraisal, beta value equals to 0.073, $p = 0.101 > 0.05$. Last but not least, the beta value for career development opportunities is equals to 0.092, $p = 0.035 < 0.05$. This shows that Training has the highest beta value of 0.663 and has the most influence on turnover intention among hospital employees in Kuala Lumpur.

6.0 DISCUSSION

The implication of employee turnover has become a serious concern in today's organization. Many factors that contribute to the increase in the turnover rate of hospital employee from time to time. This study is proposed to associate previous research findings in order to create an organized structure of employee turnover so that organizations will be aware of affecting factors that leads to turnover intention. The current study reveals, factor such as training and performance appraisal are showing highest importance in determine turnover intention among hospital employees. This is followed by job security and career development opportunities. Most importantly, strategic factor such as human resource practices should be given priority in this matter because it is important to make sure employee retention in an organization. There is a mutual relationship between employee and organization. Employees will repay in terms of their loyalty to the organization if they feel that they getting appreciation from the organization. On the other hand, managers are acting like a role model which can easily influence employee's turnover intention. Thus, managers must understand in depth the meaning and characteristics of turnover intention. As an employer, need to comprehend the real contributing factor on turnover intention among hospital employee and take a corrective action to prevent issues arise related to HRM practices which could employee look for a different job in the future.

7.0 RECOMMENDATION FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

This study has covered several directions for future studies. Specifically, future research should replicate the framework of this study in other settings, such as manufacturing, telecommunication, customer care, education and others which could bring the different insights to the body of knowledge in HRM practice and turnover literature. The results on turnover intention from different sector especially in terms of HRM practices will reveal different results. Comparative study from various sectors particularly from manufacturing, education or service sectors will be more accurate in term of identifying contributing factors for employee's turnover intention from unlike background. Expanding research area in other sectors at the same time can produce a vast view on the HRM practices. On the other hand, the regression analysis in this study shows that only 50.8% turnover intention has been identified through four independent variable that were training, job security, performance appraisal and career development opportunities among hospital

employee. In other words, there are remaining 49.2% of other relevant factors need to be identified by upcoming researchers. This is because turnover intention is attributed to many factors, not limited to training, job security, career development opportunities and performance appraisal only. In addition, the future research also need to extent the current study's quantitative design into a mixed mode design which should include additional data collection technique such as interviews to investigate the issues in depth way. This is because through interviews, more detailed information could be gain from the target respondent. By combining methods of qualitative and quantitative data collection, will increase the understanding on the influence of HRM practices on turnover intention.

8.0 CONCLUSION

The appropriate human resources management is important to enable the medical services are delivered effectively and efficiently. This research shows that HRM practices such as training, job security, career development opportunities and performance appraisal has great influence on healthcare employee's turnover intention in order to achieve patient satisfaction. All the literatures reviews has determine the necessity of HRM practices in term of achieving organization goals, and also stress on the point to develop the performance of hospital employees through periodic training in order to improve the quality of healthcare service. On the other hand, it is critical to the success of the national healthcare to reform a strong, well-motivated and highly trained medical profession.

Therefore, alternative approaches for practicing HRM practices successfully in order to reduce turnover intention among hospital employees should be determine by hospital since the practices of human resource management is crucial in most of the hospitals in Kuala Lumpur. The senior management in hospitals should have a clear strategic direction and clear objectives to improve the management of employees in the hospital.

9.0 ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I like to express my gratitude to my parents, family members and close friends for their continuous support, assistance and encouragement throughout this research project. Not forgetting, a special thanks to all my respondents for participating in the research by answering my questionnaires. I also like to express my gratitude to all Hospital Directors and Directors from

Ministry of Health who had assisted me in making sure all the questions in the questionnaire is valid and is suppose to measure what it intended to measure. I would like to sum up that this research project will not be successful without the guidance and support from everyone mentioned above.

REFERENCES

1. Abassi & Hollman, (2000). Turnover: "The real bottom line", *Public Personnel Management*, 2 (3): 333-342.
2. Aksu & Yildiz (2011). Training them young is the way to up the skills base. *Sunday/Business Times*, 29 June, p. 26.
3. Berntson, R. B. Johnson, D.M. Christen, A. Moore & Christensen, (2010). The moderating role of employability in the association between job insecurity and exit, voice, loyalty and neglect. *Economic and Industrial Democracy*, 31, pp. 215-230.
4. Briscoe, (2006). The relationship between career decision status and important work outcomes. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 71, 233–246.
5. Chang & Chen, (2002). Career information, career counselling, and career development. (7th Ed.). Needham Heights, MA: Allyn & Bacon.
6. Cohen, S.Gottlieb, B. Elwyn, S.R. Siegal & L. Underwood, (2000). Social relationships and health : Measuring and intervening in social support (pp. 3–25). New York: Oxford University Press.
7. G.R. Oldham, (1986). Job insecurity: Toward a conceptual clarity. *Academy of Management Review*, 9, 438–448.
8. Helmi, (2006). The measurement and conceptualization of career stages. *Journal of Career Development*, 17, 153–166.
9. Helliriegall, D.Raphael, Soberman, A. Peter & T. Bryant, (2001). Turnover and Job Training in Developing and Developed Countries: Evidence from Colombia and the United States.
10. Johns, (2010). "Predictors of nurses intent to stay at work in a university health centre," *Nursing and Health Sciences*, vol. 6, pp. 59-68, 2004.
11. Kuo, (2004). The relationship between Human Resource Management practices, employee commitment, and operational performance in the healthcare institutions, National Cheng Kung University, Taiwan, Taiwan.
12. Mathieu & Meneze, (2005). An Investigation of Turnover and Retention Factors of Health Professional Staff within the Eastern Cape Department of Health. Masters Thesis. Rhodes University.
13. Min, P.J. Sparks, Rachele, K. Vanessa & J. M. Kennedy, (2007). Turnover intention and preparedness for change: Exploring leader-member exchange and occupational self- efficacy as antecedents of employability predictors. *Career Development International*, 12 (7), pp. 660-679.
14. Mitchell, T. R. Raymond, Holtom, Lee, & Graske, T. (2001). How to keep your best employee: Developing an effective retention policy. *The Academy of Management Executive*, 15 (4), 96-109.
15. Moncarz, B.F. Clenney, D. Kelly, M.L. Burg & Taylor, (2009). Job Search Modes and Turnover, *Career Dev. Int.* 9(5):442-458.
16. Moynihan, Wright & Gardner, (2003). The impact of human resource management on organizational performance: progress and prospects. *Academy of Management Journal*, 39, 779-801.
17. Robbins, M. Monte, C. F. Tuttle, J.M. Coery & Kalle, (2005). Career commitment and expected utility of present job as predictors of turnover intentions and turnover behavior. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 39, 331-343.
18. Shaw, Gupta & Delery, (2005). Turnover theory at the empirical interface: Problems of fit and function. *Academy of Management Review*, 27, 346–360.
19. Sherman & Bohlander, (1992). Training, Productivity and Wages in Italy. *Labour Economic*, 12, 557-576.
20. Qurehi & Rasli, (2014). Turnover and Job Training in Developing and Developed Countries: Evidence from Colombia and the United States.
21. Quresh, Altman, K. Blau, S. Martin & Gouldner, (2013). Turnover theory at the empirical interface: Problems of fit and function. *Academy of Management Review*, 27(3), 346–360.
22. U. Sekaran & R. Bougie, (2010). *Research Methods for Business: A Skill Building Approach*, Wiley, London.
23. Wheeler, Harris & Harvey, (2010). Vocational self-concept crystallization as a mediator of the relationship between career self-management and job decision effectiveness. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 76(2), 234–243.
24. Zikmund, W. G., Babin, B. J., Carr, J. C., & Griffin, M. (2009). *Business research methods* (8th ed.) USA: South-Western College Publishing.
25. Zimmerman, (2009). Organizational Work and Absenteeism. *Psychological Bulletin*, 80, 151-176